

Afterlife in Cyberspace: Investigating Thomas Pynchon's *Bleeding Edge* through a Lens of Gothic Tradition and Postmodern Subjectivity

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Streszczenie

Recenzja, która ukazała się 28 września 2013 roku w międzynarodowym serwisie internetowym magazynu *The Guardian*, dyplomatycznie sklasyfikowała *Bleeding Edge* Thomasa Pynchona jako dzieło wielogatunkowe, co – biorąc pod uwagę różnorodność oraz złożoność wątków i koncepcji uwzględnionych w wyżej wymienionej pracy – wydawało się logiczną decyzją. Nie przeszkodziło to jednak wielu innym ówczesnym recenzentom oraz badaczom literatury poczynić własnych klasyfikacji gatunkowych, pośród których znalazły się między innymi powieść detektywistyczna, fikcja szpiegowska, literatura rewizjonistyczna i różnorakie odmiany fantastyki naukowej. Jednak dziwnym trafem niewielu zaangażowanych w lekturę akademików zwróciło uwagę na gotyckość przedłożonej narracji, potencjalną nadnaturalność opisanych zdarzeń i postaci czy na narastający w głównej bohaterce powieści lęk przed tym, co nieznane i niezrozumiałe.

Nawet w przypadku poczynienia tego typu obserwacji, przybierały one z reguły postać zdawkowych, niezobowiązujących komentarzy, nigdy nie

Oskar Zasada, dr; jest pracownikiem badawczo-dydaktycznym na Wydziale Nauk Humanistycznych Uniwersytetu Jana Długosza w Częstochowie; od 2022 roku pełni funkcję asystenta w Instytucie Literaturoznawstwa UJD; ostatnio opublikowane zostały dwa jego artykuły badawcze – *(Un)dead Stereotypes: An Analysis of the (De) evolution of the Supernatural Creature Archetypes in the iZombie Television Series* (2023) oraz *Tilting at Numbers: A Critical Analysis of the Quixotic Attitudes and Picaresque Undertones in Ramsey Campbell's The Count of Eleven* (2023); jego aktualne zainteresowania badawcze obejmują posthumanizm oraz transhumanizm w ujęciu literaturoznawczym, kosmicyzm i mechanistyczny materializm we współczesnej fikcji gotyckiej oraz przejawy subiektywności gonzo w literaturze i kinematografii amerykańskiej.

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osiągając formy pełnoprawnego procesu analitycznego. Świadczy to o wciąż obecnej luce badawczej, którą niniejszy artykuł ma zadanie wypełnić. Wstępny krok tego zamierzenia stanowić będą analiza i interpretacja ostatniej powieści Pynchona przy użyciu narracyjnych i strukturalnych perspektyw charakteryzujących klasyczne prace literatury gotyckiej. Drugi etap wywodu obejmuje krytyczne spojrzenie na motywy niesamowitości oraz technologicznej grozy, które charakteryzują fikcyjny program Deep Archer i postaci odpowiedzialne za jego stworzenie. W sekcji końcowej omówione zostaną rozmaite próby zamazania przez autora koncepcyjnych granic pomiędzy spirytualizmem i technologizacją. Mając na uwadze kluczowe aspekty literackie wywodzące się z tradycji postmodernistycznej, ostatnia część wywodu prześledzi również pogłębiającą się wraz z rozwojem fabuły subiektywność percepcji głównej bohaterki oraz wpływ stopniowo zanikającej stabilności mentalnej teje postaci na interpretację przez czytelnika świata przedstawionego.

Keywords: postmodernizm, literatura gotycka, Thomas Pynchon, technologiczna groza, wirtualna rzeczywistość

Introduction

In 2013, writer and journalist Marina Hyde, one of *The Guardian's* more prominent reviewers, classified Thomas Pynchon's *Bleeding Edge* as a multi-genre novel (par. 1), which considering the vast array of subject matter contained within, should not be surprising. Other reviewers made their own attempts at categorizing, and upon reading their articles, one might get a false impression that they have all read different books. Some have branded Pynchon's 2013 work a detective story (Gourley 2014: par. 5), others pointed out that it borders on science-fiction (Jarvis 2013: par. 4), and still others noted that it explores the posthuman condition (Siegel 2016: par. 1). Most listings of major themes included the 9/11 attacks, as well as the increasing role of technology in contemporary society.

However, very few people actually took the time to investigate the potentially supernatural elements or the mysterious and otherworldly ambiance of the novel; an oversight that this text will try to remedy by analyzing *Bleeding Edge* from a Gothic perspective and taking a closer look at the uncanny inspirations behind Deep Archer, Pynchon's fictional virtual reality environment. Would it be possible to add another label to the already impressive list of descriptors under which the book is listed? Will it actually improve or cripple textual understanding and appreciation if we decide to do so? What kinds of genres – and theme-focused interconnections can one map out by examining the various works of fiction that allegedly inspired Departure's creation? The following paragraphs attempt to answer these and other questions. In order to provide a suitable frame of reference for the intended analysis, the narrative and thematic sensibilities typical for Gothic literature will be outlined first. The next section will include a thorough juxtaposition of classic Gothic archetypes with *Bleeding Edge's* cast and a study of the more prominent character-adapting approaches found in Pynchon's 2013 bestseller. Uncanniness and the implied

supernatural will be examined in the third part, with special attention being paid to potential authorial self-insertions and to the unpredictability and unreliability of character-focused narration. The fourth section will focus on Pynchon's metafictional blurring of the lines between the mystical and the technological and on the impact that the said process can have on the reader's interpretation of the presented narrative. Finally, the article will be rounded off with a conclusion encapsulating its most important observations.

I: A Gothic frame of reference

Gothic tales employ a wide array of possible themes and framing devices, but some of these components tend to see far more usage than others. One such frequently utilized element is based on mystery mixed with potential threats. That is understandable – after all, as pointed out by Edmund Burke, there is great value to be found in obscurity when one wishes to induce fear in one's audience (Burke 1998: 54). The inability to assess the full extent of the danger creates a sense of unease in the reader – an uncertainty that is almost instantly stripped away if the author decides to provide any definite explanation. That is why, regardless of the other creative choices, some form of obscurity or secrecy is nearly always featured in works of this kind.

Unsurprisingly, the said aspects can be seen as the first (and most obvious) point of synergy between Gothic fiction and *Bleeding Edge*. In the novel, Pynchon provides these qualities by alternating between different methods of delivery – a reasonable approach, seeing as his fictional world is subject to a plethora of divisions, a great deal of which are strictly reader-dependent. The initial venue of exposure is *Bleeding Edge*'s physical reality – or the “meatspace”, as Maxine Tarnow (the novel's protagonist) refers to it (Pynchon 2013: 17%).¹ Despite its implied mundanity and plainness, this Pynchonian reimaging of post-dot-com bubble New York houses many enigmatic locales that awaken a fascination with the past. Obviously, this longing is not directed specifically towards the medieval, focusing instead on a nostalgic need to return to a more innocent time. This, once one thinks about it, was also a desire expressed in the works of Walpole and his successors (Stevens 2000: 47). Locations with an openly Gothic atmosphere are not underrepresented in Pynchon's book either. The narrative of *Bleeding Edge* contains abandoned cubicles that might be haunted (Pynchon 2013: 9%), cellars inhabited by wild animals, and even a secret underground tunnel hidden in a wine storage (Pynchon 2013: 40%).

¹ The Calibre e-book reader displays a book's percentage completion instead of individual pages.

The most flauntingly Gothic element in the book has to be the luxury apartment complex called the Deseret. Both its structure and the gruesome events that transpire within it seem to convince Maxine of its otherworldly nature. At one point, she actually compares it to a necromantic construct, a stone zombie waiting to rise after the sun has set (Pynchon 2013: 7%). There are, as previously stated, other examples of such disturbing locales, all of which form a greater framework for the unfolding plot.

And yet, one obvious dissimilarity between Pynchonian writing and Gothic sensibilities can be highlighted instantly – the story presented in *Bleeding Edge* does not offer any real sense of closure or finality. Contrastingly, nearly all of the early texts tend to resolve their complications before the narrative's conclusion. Secrets get revealed, and tyrants are removed from their seats of power. Said formula does not see much use in *Bleeding Edge*, however. Although the alleged antagonist is stopped, at least temporarily, almost nothing else gets resolved. The identity of the murderer remains unknown, as does the affiliation of the people responsible for the terrorist attack. Other characters simply move on with their lives, trying to find a place for themselves in the post-WTC world. And while ultimately false, the impression that their personal stories continue to unfold even after the narrative reaches its conclusion serves to deepen the reader's immersion. Still, the unification of Maxine's loved ones does have a weirdly Gothic sentiment to it. Not only do their bonds survive the 9/11 attacks, but the family members also experience personal growth because of the ordeal (Pynchon 2013: 99%).

The setting serves as another point of interest, and in a Gothic text it can often be seen as a character in its own right (Pradeepa 2012: 88). This notion also holds true for the yuppified version of New York presented by Pynchon as a type of conceptual counterweight for Deep Archer's virtual reality. Indeed, at the beginning of the book, the author even makes use of an epigraph by Donald Edwin Westlake. The quote provides an educated guess about what role the city of New York would play as a character in a mystery novel and offers a brief glimpse into Pynchon's thematic preferences (2013: 1%). That being noted, the Big Apple's image in *Bleeding Edge* resembles that of its many career-obsessed inhabitants; it gives off the impression of a corporate drone with a regulation haircut and a business suit. Having left most its individuality by the wayside, the metropolis engages in endless renovation and streamlining procedures to create a customer-friendly appearance – all in the hopes of increasing profitability. And while the city's impromptu persona might initially fool someone by relying on a false sense of amiability – mainly thanks to an unending slew of restaurants and recreational venues that function as faux postmodern micro-realities (Pynchon 2013: 6%, 13%, 44%) – its true sentiments, chiefly colored by callousness and apathy, are revealed soon enough.

Despite functioning as the novel's focal points, neither murders nor terrorist attacks are able to slow New York City's relentless march towards profit – and this grim realization only serves to deepen the feeling of foreboding that the reader gets exposed to more and more frequently as the story unfolds.

The *setting as character* approach is even more noticeable in connection to the constantly changing recesses of Deep Archer, which bears a lot of similarities to the creature from Mary Shelley's *Frankenstein*; so many in fact, that a short comparison seems unavoidable. In both instances the reader is able to witness manifestations of something extraordinary; the inanimate husk and the prototype program both become infused with life. The former gains sentience (Shelley 2017: 43), while the latter gets invaded by an untold number of users whose goals and motivations give rise to a virtual construct eerily reminiscent of a living being (Pynchon 2013: 15%). Just like an organism, the program starts to change, grow, and adapt, establishing a symbiotic link between itself and the fictional individuals who reside inside it. It essentially acts as a magnifying lens for the hidden desires and emotional impulses of its inhabitants, allowing them to manifest these tendencies freely in cyberspace – an uncanny situation in which an ordinary piece of code becomes something more, something that refuses all attempts at description and quantification. In fact, in both cases, the creations quickly outgrow their makers and show them the dangers of dabbling with things they do not fully understand. The monster does this directly (Shelley 2017: 144-145), while the application simply draws in misfortune in the form of human envy and greed (Pynchon 2013: 84%).² If one were to adopt a Gothic perspective, both outcomes could be seen as punishment for hubris and recklessness. Overconfident in their abilities, the program's creators expose themselves to a great deal of grief by designing it. However, the consequences they face are not as severe as in *Frankenstein's* case (Shelley 2017: 186-187); the two programmers realize the folly of their ways and are able to part with the project on reasonable terms, thereby preventing any harm from befalling them or the people they care about (Pynchon 2013: 75%).³

² The digital setting absorbs and incorporates some of the least appealing aspects of the book's physical reality (which itself are modeled after the real-life political, social, and economical inequities of the early 2000's). Indeed, *Bleeding Edge's* virtual version of the Garden of Eden seems to get tainted even more easily than its biblical predecessor. But while somewhat demoralizing, this image, when examined from the opposite perspective, also offers the reader a certain degree of insight into the everyday fictionalization of the real-world, which is evident in the ceaseless retellings, reframings, and active manipulation attempts carried out by governments, corporations, and the media outlets.

³ Incidentally, one of the tech-oriented characters actually describes his product as an example of bleeding-edge technology. This statement matches the tendency of some of the early gothic works to derive their names from setting characters, as was the case with *The Castle of Otranto* and *The Mysteries of Udolpho*.

II: (Post)modernizing Gothic archetypes

Like so many other literary genres, Gothic fiction relies on a specific cast of frequently employed character archetypes. In many instances, these models are not exceptionally fleshed out or intended to undergo a great deal of character development (Kilgour 1995: 4) – they mostly drive the tale forward by engaging in specific interactions and drawing attention to vital details. This is partially why it is not difficult to draw parallels between them and the characters presented in *Bleeding Edge*. It is safe to say that Thomas Pynchon does not labor under a realism-rooted obligation to create fictional entities who can flawlessly imitate real-life people. And while these creations are nowhere near as utilitarian as the plot-driving vehicles created by, for example, H. P. Lovecraft (Joshi 2001: 287), rounding out the psychological makeup of every character does not seem to rank high on Pynchon's list of creative priorities. However, this is not negligence – it is a conscious authorial decision. Indeed, literary scholars have remarked upon this preference for cartoon-like portrayals on several occasions (Lauzen 1986: 101; Pearce 1981: 3), and as the writer's earlier works make clear, it is not limited to secondary characters, often being employed when depicting protagonists.

Early works from the genre established by Horace Walpole usually portray their **Hero** as someone who is able to save the damsel in distress and stop the villain (Pradeepa 2012: 87). Such an individual, if not outright courageous, is at least resolute and mentally agile. Compassion and selflessness are also noteworthy personality traits that a hero should possess. If we ignore the gender aspect, Maxine Tarnow fits the profile pretty well. After all, she liberates the antagonist's love interest and prevents him from carrying out his plans (Pynchon 2013: 98%). And while no one is likely to consider Miss Tarnow needlessly reserved when it comes to matters of intimate relationships, the author does not really make any attempts to present her as a **Virgin Maiden**. The character's purity is not sexual in nature. She does, however, show great concern for the wellbeing of others, and sometimes goes out of her way to help them without receiving any sort of compensation.

Obviously, classic Gothic texts also have a clearly defined focus point in the form of an irredeemable antagonist commonly referred to as the **Tyrant** (Pradeepa 2012: 87). It is remarkable how closely Gabriel Ice follows the typical progression of this archetype. The character is initially introduced as an enigmatic and imposing despot, but this illusion is destroyed by the end of the novel. Gabriel does not confront Maxine as a nigh-unstoppable force; instead, he reveals himself to be an angry "schmuck" with tendencies for spousal abuse (Pynchon 2013: 99%). All it takes to shatter his illusions of grandeur is a single handgun that does not even fire (Pynchon 2013: 100%). Public

humiliation, combined with his crumbling delusions of grandeur force Ice to flee. And while his defeat is not permanent by any means, the fact remains that he has been thwarted by the protagonist.

And what about the character of the **Older, Foolish Woman**, who (usually) stands by the **Tyrant's** side? (Pradeepa 2012: 87) Not surprisingly, this role falls to Tallis Ice. Choosing Gabriel over her mother, Tallis obediently supports her husband's machinations and does whatever he asks of her, not unlike her complacent predecessors. Even her attempt at infidelity is not as secret as she would like to believe (Pynchon 2013: 95%). Still, unlike most of her Gothic counterparts, Tallis is eventually provided with an opportunity for redemption and personal growth. Cast out by the increasingly erratic antagonist, she finally sees the despot for who he is, and assisted by Maxine Tarnow, decides to stand up to him (Pynchon 2013: 98%).

Interestingly enough, the novel features another overtly villainous individual. However, despite having committed numerous atrocities during his time as a field operative, the character of Nicholas Windust should not be considered completely irredeemable. It is true that the government agent is deeply flawed, and that his convictions make him act in a way that is reprehensible, or even inhumane. Assuming that they are true at all, the troubling events of his past surround him with a jaded aura of cynicism, and he has his own, seemingly self-centered take on life; one that he refuses to change despite being at odds with the rest of society, or even with the reader. He causes tension and conflict with his mere presence. On the other hand, Maxine does end up falling for his impressive physique and authoritative attitude (Pynchon 2013: 23%, 53%). Infatuated with his dominant personality, she attempts to save him from the consequences of his past decisions, even when it is already too late. The act of leading one of the novel's background characters to safety likewise elevates the government spook above the status of an ordinary thug (Pynchon 2013: 93%). Cynical and arrogant, he is prone to acts of cruelty and those of genuine affection alike. All of the above traits, along with his charisma and a fanatical dedication to an ideal, combine to depict Windust as a postmodern reinterpretation of the **Byronic hero**, a character archetype fully fleshed out by the Romantics from the original **Gothic villain** (Pradeepa 2012: 86).

While fairly inconsequential and employed mostly as a means of making the narrative more entertaining for the reader, the **Ruffian** archetype was also able to secure a niche for itself in Pynchon's 2013 novel. At first presented as pure comic relief, the Russian twins Misha and Grisha appear amiable enough – their speech patterns and attitudes give off a false impression of harmlessness and approachability. It is only after they make an attempt to kidnap Gabriel Ice's significant other that one realizes how dangerous they really are. In doing so, both young men mimic the actions of their Gothic

forerunners, who were well known for riding off with distressed damsels. Similar inclinations towards foul play are hinted at by two other minor characters, the “entrepreneurs” known as Rocky and Igor, who happen to hide their potential for malice under several layers of social niceties (Pynchon 2013: 30%). Moreover, Rocky’s cultural background and implied occupation synergize well with the Italian word **bandito**, from which the discussed archetype derives its other name – **Banditti** (Pradeepa 2012: 88).

Even though *Bleeding Edge* does not feature an actual representative of the **Clergy**, Shawn, a New-Age spiritual advisor from California (Pynchon 2013: 7%), happens to be a good stand-in for this role. With his made-up biography and dubious diplomas, this hybrid of a guru and therapist would rather waste his time watching reruns of old television shows than look for any real enlightenment. His self-righteous personality and half-hearted reliance on misunderstood existential concepts also bring him closer to the classic Gothic examples of priesthood, since such persons were generally depicted as feeble and out of touch with the world around them (Pradeepa 2012: 88). Alternatively, Shawn can be considered a staple **Clown**. The banter in which he engages with Maxine during their therapeutic sessions is humorous and offers occasional words of wisdom, even if the man’s grasp on the basic tenets of his profession is rather dubious.

One of the classic archetypes that is visibly missing from Pynchon’s character lineup is the previously mentioned **Virgin Maiden** (Pradeepa 2012: 87). Then again, with her delicate disposition and a tendency to faint at a moment’s notice, such an individual would probably be an ill-fitted and tiresome addition to the cast. As a female lead, Maxine is in possession of other, more practical virtues, and implementing a separate character of this sort might have proven detrimental to the narrative; especially since the novel adopts a completely different approach to amorous subplots than early Gothic texts did. To put it mildly, *Bleeding Edge* does not shy away from sexual topics; it meticulously lists the protagonist’s past relationships and provides detailed descriptions of various sexual acts. And herein lies the problem – or perhaps another proof of Pynchon’s ability to successfully refurbish olden concepts and use them to both tilt the readers’ expectations and establish links to the contemporary sociocultural reality of the West. While they were often labeled as provocative upon publication, most classic Gothic tales simply adopted a sensualized and sensationalized approach to the sensibilities of their time (Stevens 2000: 24), handling matters of romance more subtly than typical postmodern fiction. The consummation of a relationship did not garner much attention, as the narrative tended to focus on the slow and adversity-ridden process of courtship instead (Harris 2020: par. 102-109). What is more, with the mass emergence of strong and independent heroines in all types of media, female characters who

constantly require saving and are unable to overcome the slightest adversity have (arguably) become outdated and less relatable, which provides another valid explanation for the **Virgin Maiden's** absence in the plot.

III: Implications of supernaturality

Along with the staples outlined above, supernatural elements seem to be an almost obligatory part of the Gothic legacy. In this case, the term *supernatural* refers to entities, forces, or phenomena that are “beyond scientific understanding or the laws of nature” (En.wikipedia.org 2003: par. 1). In other words, it captures what is outside or above the natural, rationally perceivable world. Assuming that the reader remains open to dramatically different interpretations of a given text – as one should be when dealing with postmodern fiction – there are plenty of potentially supernatural elements to be found in *Bleeding Edge*. Why only potentially? Partially because in one of his earlier essays, Pynchon firmly cautioned against the reckless use of supernatural elements; he indicated that if an author insists “upon fictional violations of the laws of nature,” he or she risks “being judged by the literary mainstream as Insufficiently Serious” (Pynchon 1984: par. 22).⁴ Various Gothic works were also subjected to this sort of dismissive treatment. Indeed, initially the genre as a whole tended to receive a great deal of bad press, which ran counter to the rapidly increasing numbers of its (mostly female) readership (Stevens 2000: 23). Because of their (alleged) tendency to prey upon the reader’s deep-seated need to escape the monotony of everyday life, these works were viewed by the majority of contemporaries as insidious, potentially addictive, and pandering to the basest of human emotions (Stevens 2000: 24). And seeing as attitudes of this sort seem to survive in various circles of literary criticism even today, being branded as lacking in seriousness can potentially have a detrimental impact on the reception of one’s work.

Pynchon does not really insist on the supernatural, but neither does he go out of his way to openly debunk it in *Bleeding Edge*. Just like in the case of the overarching plot, the author appears to be more content with allowing his readers to invent their own explanations of enigmatic phenomena than with forcefully invoking some sort of higher authority to solve every single issue.

⁴ In this case, “seriousness” might as well be interpreted as adopting a conformist attitude towards realist depictions. However, postmodernism does not uphold realism’s dictums. The best it can do is pay halfhearted lip service to them, all the while covertly reminding the reader that the “reality” he has come into contact with is entirely fictional and that comprehending its workings requires active participation (which occasionally borders even on co-creation). Likewise, postmodernism makes no attempts to conceal the inherent subjectivity of the process of narration – a notion which most realist writings not only disregarded, but actively attempted to quell (Nicol 2009: 27).

Indeed, Pynchon's approach to writing the unknown and the unexplained seems to resonate strongly with that of Clara Reeve. In Reeve's *The Old English Baron*, which is a reimagining of Horace Walpole's *Otranto*, the fantastic elements of the original have been downplayed in order to make them less obvious and absurd. This form of presentation questioned the presence of the supernatural, but did not utterly deny its existence (Geary 1992: 40) – just like in the case of *Bleeding Edge*, which presents its readership with a wide variety of interpretative approaches. In fact, in this regard Pynchon's work goes one step further than the Gothic writings because the readings it contains are not mutually exclusive; they all possess a degree of inherent validity and interconnectedness.⁵

Firstly, what about the character of Marvin, the enigmatic ex-deliverman? He always appears out of nowhere and has an unusual tendency for providing Maxine with things that she might not want, but ends up needing along the way. Dossiers, recordings, ice cream flavors that have been discontinued long ago – there seems to be nothing that this curious individual cannot get his hands on. Should we follow the protagonist's train of thought and perceive Marvin as some sort of otherworldly messenger (Pynchon 2013: 23%), perhaps even an angel employed by equally perplexing forces? After all, he cannot even be contacted, appearing instead at a time of his own choosing. Or maybe a more metafictional interpretation is in order, one that would be more in line with the postmodern narratives of Jorge Luis Borges and Philip K. Dick? Perhaps Marvin is simply an undercover **author avatar**, secretly supporting his characters as they make their way through the narrative?⁶

On a similar note, some of the other background characters featured in the novel claim to possess abilities unavailable to ordinary humans. One of these is Conkling Speedwell, a man blessed with a superhuman sense of smell which he (allegedly) employs as a tool in his forensic investigations (Pynchon 2013: 42%). Another character, mentioned in passing by the nasal investigator, is supposed to be proösmic – able to foreshadow things that are going to happen in the near future (Pynchon 2013: 50%). When confronted with such claims, is the reader supposed to explain them away as a string of

⁵ To better comprehend the intricacy of this phenomenon, the reader might wish to familiarize themselves with the household analogy presented in Mary McCarthy's 'A Bolt from the Blue' (2002: 83). Although initially outlined to showcase the intricacies of Nabokov's *Pale Fire*, it can prove extremely useful when applied to other examples of postmodern fiction.

⁶ Unfortunately, even though quite intriguing, this reading does not mesh well with Pynchon's usual approach to narration. Although frequently encountered among other postmodern writers, the literary device of self-insertion, appears to go directly against the creative preferences of *Bleeding Edge*'s author. And while this observation is based solely on the contents of Pynchon's previous publications, it does establish a somewhat humorous interlink with the reclusive reputation he has garnered over the years (Sometrubadour 2010: 3:35-3:57).

random coincidences or award them with a modicum of plausibility, thereby accepting sensuality's edge over mundane reasoning?⁷

To follow up on this question, does seeing dead individuals move about of their own volition imply that the viewer is exceedingly sensual or outright insane? Both Maxine and her therapist admit to noticing individuals who are known to have died. A cynical mind would be quick to interpret their confessions as a result of some form of hysteria or survivor's guilt connected to the World Trade Center terrorist attacks – an assessment that might well be correct from a Burkean or Freudian point of view. And yet, ghosts and their interactions with the living are one of the more prominent staples of Gothic; the apparitions deliver warnings, seek revenge, and, on occasion, even long for intimate physical contact, as shown in Lewis' *The Monk* (2002: 163). But the specters in *Bleeding Edge's* "meatspace" do no such things. Their presence, real or imagined, is only mentioned in passing; still, it makes the book's already notable Gothic ambiance more prominent in the process.

Specters are not the only example of physical-world uncanniness that Miss Tarnow runs into. Incorporated by Pynchon into the novel, the Montauk Project conspiracy is able to leave its mark on the protagonist as well. Throughout the majority of the book, the concept of time travelling government operators is represented fairly subtly – that is until the heroine actually witnesses a temporal anomaly on her way through the city (Pynchon 2013: 71%). And while likely not related to spontaneous time distortions, Maxine's interaction with a character named Uncle Dizzy later on in the novel constitutes another bewildering encounter, since the old man apparently vanishes into thin air, leaving Tarnow flabbergasted as to what exactly happened (Pynchon 2013: 90%). Still, a skeptical reader is likely to classify these scenes as examples of highly intense introspective episodes, during which the main character proceeds to shut out the outside world, including most temporal and spatial stimuli. But even if one accepts this rationale as plausible, it is worth noting that, regardless of the exact nature of the depicted events, the multifaceted structure of Pynchon's narrative challenges the reader to keep track not only of variables connected to time and space, but also of those rooted in the dimension of the mind. Moreover, if one takes into account the inability to differentiate between real and virtual occurrences that Maxine develops later on in the story, the above incidents can be interpreted as scripted events taking place in *Deep Archer*.

The lead character's dreams also fall into the category of the supposedly supernatural. If not outright prophetic, they are at least exceedingly detailed

⁷ As might be expected, this perspective was frequently employed in the works of Gothic tradition (Stevens 2000: 19).

and contain a high amount of symbolism. They tend to mirror the events that transpire later on in the novel – ones that she actively partakes in, as well as those that lie beyond her field of influence. To draw a line of comparison, in *The Old English Baron* the protagonist also experiences vivid dreams that hold a deep connection to his current situation (Reeve 2007: 7, 8, 36). Of course, in the case of Pynchon's somewhat unstable heroine, these could be seen as subtle representations of work-related tension and sexual frustration.

IV: Digitalizing the arcane

Bleeding Edge's many attempts at blurring the line between technology and the occult also deserve attention. Naturally, these efforts on the part of the author bring to mind the third of Arthur C. Clarke's laws, which proclaims that "any sufficiently advanced technology is indistinguishable from magic" (1972: 130). And if that is indeed the case, then even malicious software qualifies, which becomes clearly evident when Maxine considers the face-to-face aspects of zapper fraud. The knowledge of the program's hidden features is meant to be shared verbally, bestowed by one individual to another like some warped version of mystical knowledge passed by "rogue rabbis to apprentices in kabbalah" (Pynchon 2013: 19%). Likewise, the partnership that one of the programmers establishes with a Latina sorceress in order to take down the story's antagonist reveals that the Pynchonian version of the Internet "exhibits a strange affinity for the dynamics of curses, especially when written in the more ancient languages predating HTML" (Pynchon 2013: 72%). The combination of hack-induced data loss and real-world hindrances brought about by the hex, while never fully explored in the book, gives rise to an intriguing notion of interconnectivity between technology and the mystic arts. And is an idea of this sort really that implausible? After all, postmodern fiction has successfully carried out conceptual fusions and subversions that were far less organic and believable.⁸

And then, there is one of the novel's focal points – the aforementioned fictional virtual reality program known as Deep Archer – or maybe Departure, a name that is frequently employed interchangeably and proves to be more fitting on multiple occasions. The software's original concept seemed innocent enough – to provide a virtual sanctuary for people who became disenchanted with the real world. Indeed, upon encountering such a description one could

⁸ The woodlouse narrator from the first chapter of Barnes' *A History of the World in 10½ Chapters* instantly come to mind, as does Kurt Vonnegut's critically acclaimed *Slaughterhouse-Five* with its temporally-unhinged, zoo-imprisoned war veteran.

easily classify the said program as a postmodernist reinterpretation of virtual world platforms such as *VR Chat* or *Second Life*. However, unlike these applications – and despite one of the novel's background character's claims to the contrary – *Departure* possesses a list of inspirations which is firmly rooted in the philosophical and the metaphysical, and the works that can be found on the said list cover ideas ranging from existentialism to trans- and posthumanism. As a point of interest, this section will also feature a short juxtaposition of the major themes found in these titles with the ones in *Bleeding Edge*. This will be done in order to illustrate that the conceptual elements which these influences are famous for can be linked not only to the fictional program but also, in a truly metafictional fashion, to the novel that serves as its source.

One of the inspirations listed by Lucas is *Ghost in the Shell*, a media franchise created by Masamune Shirow, who in turn drew a fair amount of his ideas from Arthur Koestler's work in philosophical psychology called *The Ghost in the Machine*. As a cyberpunk setting, Shirow's brainchild is characterized by an (over)abundance of ideas about the human soul and the ways it interacts with future technology. It analyzes the consequences of merging an individual's body with artificial implants and the risks of digitalizing a person's consciousness. More importantly, it features a globe-spanning information network. Apart from other functions, this construct serves as a virtual reality in which disembodied identities can interact with one another and seek shelter from the physical world. This, of course, makes it eerily similar to *Deep Archer*.⁹

Akira, an animated movie from 1988, is listed as another inspiration. Set in a semi-fictional city called Neo-Tokyo, the film has strong philosophical undercurrents infused with concepts taken from various post- and transhumanistic paradigms. Curiously enough, its story meshes quite well with the ideas formulated by Friedrich Nietzsche, specifically the **will to power** and (to a slightly lesser extent) the *Übermensch* (Richardson 1996: 18, 66). The animation's antagonist is an obvious example of these driving forces, but they can also be noticed by examining the final stage of Pynchon's *Departure*, during which every user is able exercise their power and inventiveness to perform truly miraculous feats. Likewise, the creative potential possessed by children is illustrated in both *Bleeding Edge* and in *Akira*. The first work shows it by presenting the reader with digital reconstruction of New York created by Maxine's progeny (Pynchon 2013: 90%). The second one is less subtle,

⁹ Still, it should be noted that the idea of full-immersion virtual reality is far older, and its literary presence can be traced back at least to Laurence Manning's short story series 'The Man Who Awoke' (1933). The term **cyberspace** was introduced nearly half a century later, in William Gibson's 'Burning Chrome' (1982), but the concept became entrenched in popular culture only after he included it in his 1984 novel, *Neuromancer*.

portraying a disturbed young man who unlocks within himself the ability to reconfigure the structure of matter by using willpower (Otomo 1988: 1:44:00-1:45:00). Incidentally, Nietzsche likewise refers to the third and final step of his *Übermensch* metamorphosis as the **child stage** (2006: 16). Nevertheless, one should keep in mind that great power, when not kept under control, can begin to act out on its own. Coming to terms with this realization, *Departure's* creators are forced to open source it in order to minimize the danger it poses and keep everyone safe (Pynchon 2013: 75%). Contrastively, the character of Tetsuo proves unable to relinquish his god-like gifts and becomes hideously warped by the energies coursing within him.¹⁰

Finally, there is Hideo Kojima's *Metal Gear Solid*, the third installment in a long-running video game series. Considering that it serves as an example of an interactive medium and that its creator is referred to as "God" by one of Deep Archer's programmers (Pynchon 2013: 15%), one would expect to find at least a handful of noteworthy influences that MGS had on the fictional program. But *Departure* is not an action game. In fact, as Pynchon is quick to remind us, it is not a game at all. Still, both of these applications are close, at least in terms of agency; each offers the user a degree of control in virtual environs. Then again, the program dreamt up by Bleeding Edge's author does not have a uniform plot, and the setting, while standardized at the beginning, quickly becomes individual for each user. Even the graphics cannot be compared accurately, as the visuals in *Departure* are leagues ahead of anything released in 2001 and appear to be structured around some convoluted form of community-shared content. With this in mind, one could feasibly interpret the program's multipronged evolution as a metaphor for postmodern fiction, since, as previously mentioned, works of this kind tend to accommodate most readings, saddling the reader with his own share of creative duties in the process. However, when taking into account a subtitle like *Tactical Espionage Action*, it suddenly becomes far easier to find similarities between *Metal Gear Solid* and *Bleeding Edge* as a whole. Both works feature many examples of spy-related activity, and the characters that the protagonists encounter during their respective investigations cannot be trusted to divulge their true affiliations. Various attempts at infiltration are made in physical and virtual environs, and weapons of mass destruction are constructed behind closed doors. Each of the stories also deals with supposed terrorist threats, and in both narratives, the true identities of the people responsible are not clearly specified.

¹⁰ An analogy to Gabriel Ice's steady loss of authority can be made at this point as well. As someone who aims to continuously extend his proverbial grasp, he actively aspires to evoke the **will to power**, but ultimately fails horribly. The plan to acquire the application backfires, his wife leaves and is likely to take their child with her, and he himself forfeits his imposing demeanor.

Moreover, the refusal to provide his readers with easy answers foregrounds one of Pynchon's more prominent metafictional preferences, the penchant for creating plots within plots – or in other words, a tendency to infuse his event sequences with an overabundance of intrigues, machinations, and **red herrings**, thereby causing a bloat of (mis)information which disrupts linearity, increases interchangeability, and eventually completely derails the investigative attempts of both the reader and the protagonist. The technique in question was of great use to postmodern writers such as Umberto Eco and Ishmael Reed, but Thomas Pynchon employs it on a truly overwhelming scale. Furthermore, in the case of his writings, the process also doubles as a blatant reference to the conspiratorial worldview of countless US citizens – a perspective he himself is known for (Walsh 2013: par. 17).

Analogously, without the additional information found in its prequels and sequels, both the character profiles and the ideological paradigm presented by *Metal Gear Solid* are woefully incomplete. Still, the sequence of events portrayed in the game points to the conclusion that power – regardless of its source or the form it takes – makes it possible for the one who wields it to have the final word in society, or even to rise above societal limitations – a viewpoint that Gabriel Ice would likely agree with. In one of the game's many plot-related expositions, a scientist nicknamed Otacon notes that the greatest technological breakthroughs are made when military conflict looms on the horizon (IStreamPS5 2022: 11:40-11:54), and while this claim would be debatable in relation to the real world, in the fictional universe of *Metal Gear* it holds a lot of weight. It also seems to synergize well with Pynchon's narrative framing, since Deep Archer emerges and undergoes its initial changes just before the breakout of the "War on Terror" (Pynchon 2013: 68%). The previously mentioned game character sums up his speech by falling back on an old truism: inventors should take responsibility for their creations. Departure's programmers appear to share this sentiment, and their decision to open source the application potentially prevents a dangerous weapon from falling into the wrong hands. They however, expand upon the previous concept by making the product free. After all, responsibility should not be limited solely to the creators, but extended to all the people who choose to benefit from their invention – especially if one can only reap these benefits by crossing the threshold of physical reality and traversing the unknown and malleable reaches of cyberspace.

Indeed, if nothing else, Deep Archer invokes the sublime – in this context seen as a set of human reactions to "an overwhelming experience that transcends everyday normality" (Stevens 2000: 50). On more than one occasion, Maxine has to remind herself that what she is interacting with is just code. And yet, during her visit to the already open-sourced program, it is stated that the "ship"

she is on is headed for “a horizon between the coded and the codeless” (Pynchon 2013: 74%).¹¹ Similarly, in a declaration that adds further credence to the notion that the barriers separating the book’s two settings are slowly beginning to dissolve – and which the protagonist classifies as an “*act of naïve faith or raving insanity*” (Pynchon 2013: 78%) – the two previously described representatives of the Ruffian archetype exclaim that Departure is not just a program. They go on to state that it is an actual place, an asylum that takes in everyone, making no distinction between the living and the dead. Upon reading these two descriptions, Edward Burke’s treatise on the ideas of the sublime and beautiful comes to mind once more, bringing with it mystical and religious connotations. While Pynchon’s interpretation of the Deep Web can be described as a cybernetic graveyard full of old websites and discontinued applications (one that is on the verge of being yuppified and commercialized), Deep Archer serves as its direct conceptual opposite (at least initially). As all approaches to the afterlife, it is veiled in mystery and rooted almost entirely in speculation.

However, unlike many of the typical depictions of life after death, the program accommodates different levels of self-awareness. The lowest of these is reserved for the drones commemorating the people who died during the WTC attacks – simplistic bots with faces scanned from family photos, providing the victims with a mockery of life after death that would likely give even Sigmund Freud pause (Pynchon 2013: 74%). Then there is the more active (and possibly even sentient) sort, represented by the manifestations of two characters who, according to the rules of the book’s physical reality, are supposed to be dead. Are they impostors whose intent is to cause confusion and spread disinformation? Examples of highly advanced subprograms? Or maybe digitalized souls? Of course, the last option implies that one of the readings supplied by Pynchon actually presents individuals as being synonymous with data. Such an approach works on (at least) two levels. Firstly, drawing attention to the made-up nature of characters is typical of postmodern metafiction, and it defies the reader’s expectations by destabilizing his immersion and forcing him to deal with the fact that the “people” whose exploits he has been following are really just deception-oriented strings of letters made up by the author.¹² The second function of this technique is cautionary; it highlights the fact that our contemporary reality actually houses groups and institutions which actively propagate such dehumanizing paradigms in relation to genuine human beings – profit-obsessed conglomerates and corporations whose decisions are based on the notion that lives are just numbers.

¹¹ In this instance, the ship is employed both as a metaphor for the entirety of the fictional program and as a virtual venue of the protagonist’s visit.

¹² Such realizations frequently make the reader reflect not only upon the ideological nature of the presented content, but also about how he, as the medium’s recipient, interacts with such elements.

Conclusion

As the examples above clearly illustrate, there is a notable level of thematic sympathy between *Bleeding Edge* and the works of Gothic fiction, even if the concepts stemming from the latter obviously get filtered through a post-modern lens. Thanks to a highly effective fusion of dread and uncertainty, the ambience exerted by the novel has the potential to create great unease in the reader. The setting and the locations that serve as its building blocks possess an openly Gothic atmosphere as well – even the areas that have been completely yuppified and turned into substandard mini-realities which only serve to propagate reductionist portrayals of the sociocultural concepts they were modelled on. And while these venues do indeed seem fake and hollow, Pynchon's postmodern narration is able to utilize their hollowness to infuse the reader with a sense of apprehension that is undeniably realistic. As for the classic Gothic archetypes, they too respond satisfactorily to the undertaken comparison. From the **Hero** to the **Clown**, an overwhelming majority of them fit the profiles of Pynchon's fictional individuals, even if some of the said templates had to undergo a slight degree of conceptual tweaking to make them more responsive to postmodern sensibilities. The novel also provides an abundance of potentially supernatural elements to choose from, such as angelic messengers, dream visions, and cybernetically-themed undead entities. Remaining true to the tenets of postmodernism, these depictions permeate the narrative in subtle but meaningful ways, offering a myriad of interpretations, all of which are equally valid. Similarly, the philosophical and metaphysical undertones epitomized by the works that influenced Deep Archer's creation pervade not only the fictional program, but Pynchon's entire novel, revealing a web of metafictional interconnections between the real and the imagined which is sure to give even the most obstinate of readers a new outlook on fiction. But is all of the above enough to label *Bleeding Edge* as Gothic? And is another label really necessary? In all honesty, while such a categorization is indeed possible, from a scholarly standpoint the knowledge of the work's conceptual and thematic affinities is satisfactory enough on its own. What is more, the refusal to carry out such a reductionist classification synergizes rather well with Gothic literature's deep-seated affection for all things mysterious and with Pynchon's unwillingness to provide his readership with ready-made solutions.

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